

THE IMPROVED PLY CRACKING RESISTANCE OF THIN-PLY LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: In conventional multidirectional laminates, matrix/interface cracks occur prematurely in plies with fibers oblique to the loading much before final failure. However, laminates fabricated with thinner plies, called the thin-ply laminates, are able to avoid ply cracking almost up to final laminate failure. The present paper presents further results on the ply cracking and delamination resistance of these thin-ply laminates under static and cyclic tensile loadings. While thinner ply reduces ply cracking and delamination, it does not appear to improve strength and fatigue lifetime as thick-ply laminates have almost the same strength and life as thin-ply laminates even after extensive ply cracking and delamination. This may be another manifestation of final failure of laminates being fiber-controlled.

KEYWORDS: Ply thickness, Thin ply, Transverse cracking, Delamination, Cyclic loading. Tensile properties.

INTRODUCTION

In multidirectional laminates, matrix/interface cracks occur in plies with fibers oblique to the loading much before final failure. Such ply cracking has been studied extensively as it is the first failure mode in laminated composites [1-14]. A large number of models have been proposed to predict the ply crack formation and the subsequent property degradation under tensile loading. Some of these models use the effective longitudinal modulus, Poisson's ratio, and shear modulus of constituent plies varying with crack density, and use various approaches such as shear lag model [1-9], self-consistent approach [10], variational analysis [11-13], and finite difference method [14].

A toughened resin is generally used to improve the resistance to ply cracking. Another approach, however, is to use thinnest possible plies. The difficulty with the latter approach is the fabrication of thinner plies than currently available. Many authors have shown relations between ply thickness and ply cracking. However, their investigation were limited to laminates fabricated with traditional prepregs 0.12mm thick.

Recently, prepregs much thinner than conventional ones have become available [14, 15]. The laminates fabricated with these thin plies were shown to be able to avoid ply cracking almost up to the final laminate failure under static loading. Such improvement in ply cracking resistance is in line with predictions based on a combination of a stress criterion and an energy criterion. The present paper shows what improvements can be obtained in ply cracking resistance under tensile static and fatigue loadings, using both a replication technique and electrical resistance measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

T800HB graphite fiber, which is widely used for aerospace structures, was chosen as reinforcement. 12K fiber tows were spread using a new technique [16] and impregnated with BT250E-1 epoxy resin to make thin prepreg plies. The thickness of the resulting prepreps is 0.04mm which is about one third the thickness of a conventional prepreg.

Three kinds of stacking sequence were chosen to study the effect of sublaminant thickness, Table 1. A sublaminant is unidirectional with all fibers aligned in the same direction. In the following discussions, a sublaminant is sometimes called a ply. Thus, the three types of laminates listed in Table 1 are called the thin-ply laminate, the normal-ply laminate, and the thick-ply laminate, respectively. Their nominal ply thicknesses are 0.04mm, 0.12mm, 0.48mm, respectively.

All laminates consist of 48 prepreg plies, resulting in a nominal thickness of 1.92 mm. The test specimens are 280 mm long and 20 mm wide. Aluminum tabs 40mm long were attached at each end leaving a gage length of 200 mm. A schematic of test specimens is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1: Stacking sequences and layer thicknesses of test laminates

Laminate Name	Stacking sequence	Effective ply thickness
Thick-ply laminate	$[0_{12}/90_{12}]_s$	0.48mm
Normal-ply laminate	$[(0_3/90_3)_4]_s$	0.12mm
Thin-ply laminate	$[(0/90)_{12}]_s$	0.04mm

Fig. 1: Dimensions of test specimen in mm

Some specimens were polished on one of their edges for replication to monitor ply cracking using replication technique, Fig. 1. Polishing was done using sand papers with decreasing abrasive sizes: #600 followed by #1200 and then #2400. The edges were further smoothed using a polishing cloth with 0.3 micron powder. The final finishing using 0.01 micron powder gave a mirror like surface. Each of the last two steps took more than 30 min.

Three specimens of each lay-up were tested in tension at a crosshead speed of 1.27 mm/min. One specimen with a polished edge was loaded incrementally to failure to allow edge replications. That is, loading was stopped at a predetermined level and edge replication was

taken. Thereafter the load was increased to the next higher level and the same procedure was repeated.

Tension-tension fatigue tests were conducted at a stress ratio of $R=0.1$ with a sine waveform under load-control. Four different levels of maximum strain were selected: 0.8%, 0.9%, 1.0%, and 1.2%. The loading frequency was 0.1 Hz for the first cycle, 1 Hz up to the next 100 cycles, and then 7 Hz thereafter. Tests were terminated at 10^6 cycles. Fatigue testing was stopped intermittently to allow edge replication.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static properties

Tensile properties under static loading are summarized in Table 2. The measured Young's moduli appear to support the hypothesis that a smaller thickness results in a higher fiber volume fraction. However, no clear trend is observed with failure stress and strain.

Table 2: Summary of average tensile properties measured under static loading

Laminate type	Thickness / mm	Young's Modulus / GPa	Tensile strength / MPa	Maximum strain / %
Thick-ply	2.076	85.4	1140	1.41
Normal-ply	2.274	75.5	1170	1.46
Thin-ply	2.109	81.6	1180	1.38

The stress-strain curves in Fig. 2 are quite linear to final failure regardless of the ply thickness. In thick-ply laminates, microcracking occurs in the 90-degree plies in both thick-ply and normal-ply laminates. Furthermore, thick-ply laminates show delamination at the 0/90 interface. However, these damages did not result in any knee points in the stress-strain curves.

Fig. 2: Stress-strain curves under static loading

Laminate properties were calculated using the unidirectional properties of Table 3 in the classical laminate theory. The resulting modulus is 80.9 GPa, which, as expected, is comparable to those measured values listed in Table 2. If 0-degree and 90-degree plies were

completely separated and 90-degree plies carried no load, the resulting modulus would be one half the longitudinal modulus, 75 GPa. The maximum modulus reduction resulting from a full delamination will thus be about 7%. The actual reduction would, however, be less than this value, and that is the reason why the stress-strain curves appear to remain straight to final failure.

Table 3: Material properties used in the calculation

T800 / BT250E-1	Material properties
$E_{0\text{degree}} / \text{GPa}$	150
$E_{90\text{degree}} / \text{GPa}$	9
$G/d_0 / \text{GPa/mm}$	100
L / mm	100
Longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient / $10^{-6}/\text{degreeC}$	-1.5[9]
Transverse thermal expansion coefficient / $10^{-6}/\text{degreeC}$	34.3[9]
Stress free temperature/ degree C	120

Failed specimens are shown in Fig. 3. In thick-ply laminates, 90-degree plies are broken into small pieces at final failure site, as shown in Fig. 3(a). Normal-ply laminates, on the other hand, still have all plies held together although some delamination is seen at final failure location, Fig. 3(b). No delamination is observed in thin-ply laminates, Fig. 3(c), and the failure looks like that of a homogeneous material.

Fig. 3: Modes of failure under static tensile loading

The free edge normal stress in a laminate coupon of thickness h subjected to a uniaxial load is proportional to the interlaminar free-edge moment M_z

$$M_z = \int_0^{h/2} \sigma_y z dz$$

where σ_y is the in-plane ply stress normal to the edge calculated from the laminated plate theory in the absence of the free edge. This stress is independent of the lay-up for the three laminates studied. However, the interlaminar free-edge moment is the largest for thick-ply laminate and the smallest for thin-ply laminate. As the free-edge normal stress is proportional to the interlaminar free-edge moment, thick-ply laminate is most susceptible to delamination.

Fig. 4: Total microcrack lengths under static loading

Figure 4 shows total microcrack lengths in the 50-mm gage section increasing with applied strain. Total microcrack length is the sum of all microcrack lengths. Initial microcracking of thick-ply laminate occurs at 0.2% strain with the total microcrack length reaching a saturation value of 3.5 cm around 0.9% strain level. Part of the reason for such saturation behavior is the extensive delamination at the 0/90 ply interfaces. Delamination is usually initiated at the edge of a microcrack and then propagates along the interface.

Microcracking in normal-ply laminate starts at a higher strain level of 0.7% and then increases rapidly as the strain increases. The total microcrack length in normal-ply laminate is larger than that in thick-ply laminate as there is less delamination in the former. No delamination with less microcracking is in thin-ply laminate.

The effect of ply thickness on ply cracking may be investigated using the equation proposed by Takeda [6]. In terms of the parameters shown in Fig. 5, the applied strain ε_o where a set of cracks with spacing $2L$ appears is given by

$$\varepsilon_o = \left(\frac{G_T}{E_2} \frac{2bE_1 \zeta}{bE_1 + dE_2} \frac{1}{\tanh(\zeta L)} \right)^{1/2} - \varepsilon_2^T \quad (1)$$

$$\xi^2 = \frac{G}{d_0} \left(\frac{1}{E_1 b} + \frac{1}{E_2 d} \right) \quad (2)$$

where G_T is the critical energy release rate of sublaminates 2 (90-ply), and G and d_0 are the shear modulus and thickness, respectively, of interlaminar shear layer. The thermal residual strain ε_2^T in sublaminates 2 is given by

$$\varepsilon_2^T = \frac{-bE_1(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)}{(bE_1 + dE_2)} \cdot \Delta T \quad (3)$$

where α_1 and α_2 are thermal expansion coefficients. Note that sublaminates 2 consists of two 90-degree plies and sublaminates 1 consists of the remaining plies. Thus, E_2 in Eq. (1) is equal

to E_{90} in Table 3, and E_1 is the effective Young's modulus of the remaining sublaminates, Table 4.

Fig. 5: Analytical model of a cross-ply laminate with ply cracks

Table 4: Parameter for prediction of ply cracking

Type of laminate	E_1 / GPa	E_2 / GPa	d / mm	b / mm
Thin-ply	82.6	9	0.04	0.92
Normal-ply	89.6	9	0.12	0.84
Thick-ply	150	9	0.48	0.48

If the first ply crack is assumed to occur in the middle 90-degree ply at the center of the specimen, the corresponding first ply cracking strain is obtained from Eq. (1) by taking $L = L_s/2$, where L_s is the specimen length.

Unfortunately, not all properties are known to allow Eq. (1) to predict the effect of ply thickness. Therefore, a typical value of 100 J/m^2 is used for the critical energy release rate. The effective interlaminar shear layer property G/d_0 is then obtained from Eq. (1) by substituting the average measured first ply cracking strain of 0.8%. The result is $G/d_0 = 30 \text{ GPa/mm}$. For epoxies, a typical modulus is $\sim 3 \text{ GPa}$, and hence the calculated shear layer thickness is 0.1 mm, which is much thicker than reasonable. A lower value of critical energy release rate yields a smaller shear layer thickness. In fact, $G_T = 55 \text{ J/m}^2$ results in $G/d_0 = 100$, which was used in [7].

Figure 6 shows the first ply cracking (FPC) strains of a family of laminates $[(0_n/90_n)_{12/n}]_s$ predicted by Eq. (1) using $G_T = 100 \text{ J/m}^2$ and $G/d_0 = 30 \text{ GPa/mm}$. The calculated residual strain is 0.28%. The predictions are seen to be in good agreement when $n = 1$. However, the predicted strain is higher than the experimental value when $n = 12$.

Fatigue behavior

Figure 7 shows relations between maximum fatigue strains and the resulting life cycles. All 3 laminates survive 10^6 cycles when the maximum fatigue strain is below 0.8%. The limited amount of data appears to indicate that normal-ply laminate has longer fatigue life than the other two laminates at the higher strain levels.

Fig. 7: Relations between maximum fatigue strain and cycles to failure

Figure 8 shows the total microcrack lengths increasing under cyclic loading. Microcracking is fully developed within the first 10 or so cycles in thick-ply laminates, Fig. 8(a). At the strain levels tested the total microcrack length does not increase much in fatigue. The prevalent delamination reduces transverse stresses within 90-degree plies, thereby preventing further microcracking. On the other hand, microcracking in normal-ply laminates do not show any sign of slowing down up to failure or 10^6 cycles, whichever occurs earlier, Fig. 8(b). The total microcrack lengths in normal-ply laminates are much larger than in thick-ply laminates under the same conditions. As in static tension, the least amount of microcracking is observed in thin-ply laminates, Fig. 8(c). Note that even final failure occur without much microcracking in thin-ply laminates.

More extensive damage is observed in fatigue failures, Fig. 9. The 90-degree plies are seen to be broken into small pieces and detached from the 0-degree plies almost throughout the entire gage length in thick-ply laminate, Fig. 9(a). A much more contained damage with some delamination is observed in normal-ply laminate, Fig. 9(b). As in static tension, the failure of thin-ply laminate resembles that of a homogeneous brittle coupon, Fig. 9(c).

(a) Thick-ply

(b) Normal-ply

(c) Thin-ply

Fig. 8: Relations between total microcrack length and number of cycles

(a-1) Front

(b-1) Front

(c-1) Front

(a-2) Side

(b-2) Side

(c-2) Side

(a) Thick-ply

(b) Normal-ply

(c) Thin-ply

Fig. 9: Final failure modes under cyclic loading

CONCLUSIONS

The overall objective of this work was to investigate the feasibility of improving matrix cracking resistance of composite laminates by reducing ply thickness. Specifically, ply cracking resistance was investigated under static and cyclic loadings using cross-ply laminates made of thin prepreg plies which have recently become available.

As expected, thin-ply laminates with individual plies as thin as 0.04mm show much better resistance to ply cracking and delamination under both static and fatigue loadings. In fact, in thin-ply laminates no delamination is observed until final failure although some ply cracking is visible. The same behavior is observed in fatigue as well. However, thin-ply laminates

show almost the same strength and fatigue life as thick-ply laminates. This reinforces the prevailing thinking that final failure of a laminate is mostly controlled by fibers even in the presence of ply cracking and delamination. The benefits of thin-ply laminates are therefore found in the reduction of ply cracking and delamination.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The present paper is based on work supported by the Air Force Office of Scientific Research under Grant F49620-02-1-0414 with Dr. B. Les Lee as the Program Manager. The authors thank Dr. Jeff Welsh of AFRL/VS for his interest in and support of the work. Appreciation is extended to Fukui Prefecture and Bryte Technology Inc. for supplying the laminates.

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